

Rotational Invariance, Momentum Conservation, Fermat's Principle and Free Particle Quantum Mechanics

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In classical mechanics, a free particle moving in a uniform medium with no forces has rotational invariance. The particle can move with a momentum p (linked with impulse) in any direction. This rotational invariance is broken if there is a target (e.g. a small plane) lying in some direction. In such a case, the momentum perpendicular to the plane will undergo an impulse, while that parallel, will not, i.e it will be conserved. The direction of momentum in 3-space is important because of possible interactions. In order to find the components of momentum, one may use $p \sin(\theta)$, for example, where p is the magnitude and $\sin(\theta) = x/L = d/dx (\sqrt{xx + yy + zz})$ where yy and zz are held constant. If one begins with a momentum, it becomes linked with a spatial position (x/L or y/L or z/L) because of possible interactions. This spatial length is linked with the operator (translational generator) d/dx_i or the rotationally invariant $\sqrt{xx+yy+zz}$.

As a first step, if one has a two dimensional refraction-problem with a surface along the x axis (n_1 - n_2 index of refraction interface), then there are two rays, one in n_1 and the other in n_2 such that $d/dx (\sqrt{xx + AA})$ and $d/dx (\sqrt{(L-x)(L-x) + AA})$ represent p components parallel to the surface where momentum is conserved. These two p components are equal allowing one to write one minus the other equals 0. Given that d/dx appears (to break rotational symmetry), the equation has the form of a maximization of time, i.e. Fermat's Least Time Principle, but is really linked to the idea of breaking rotational symmetry to show momentum conservation parallel to the surface and a lack of momentum conservation perpendicular.

We suggest that the above idea may be taken further because one may create an eigenfunction or $-i\hbar d/dx$, namely $\exp(ipx)$. $-i\hbar d/dx$ yields the x -component of p which may be conserved or involved in a target collision. A key point, however, is that $-i\hbar d/dx$ is self-adjoint so that $\exp(ipx)$ s are orthogonal. This means that if they are considered to act like probability (multiply for AND), then orthogonality of the functions ensures momentum conservation. The above ideas are purely classical, but give rise to free particle quantum mechanics.

Rotational Invariance in Classical Mechanics

We try to argue in this note that $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$, the quantum mechanical free particle wavefunction, follows from strictly classical notions about rotational invariance and its breaking. For a classical particle moving in uniform space with no forces, there is rotational invariance. The particle may move in any direction and all seem the same.

Rotational invariance, however, is broken if one has targets in this space with particular orientations and locations. Given that momentum is linked to impulse, it is the variable of concern. As a result, one must go beyond the notion of a p magnitude and an arbitrary direction. An x - y - z co-ordinate system needs to be placed in the space so one may describe the orientation-position of a target as well as the p components parallel and perpendicular to the

target. The parallel components do not undergo an impulse, hence these have momentum conservation, while the perpendicular one does receive an impulse.

To find $p(x)$, $p(y)$, $p(z)$ from the magnitude p , one may use, as an example,

$$p(x) = x/\sqrt{xx+yy+zz} = \sin(\theta) = d/dx \text{ partial} (\sqrt{xx+yy+zz}) \quad ((1))$$

with, $yy+zz$ is held constant. As a result, because of possible interactions, the rotationally invariant p magnitude is now associated with a spatial length and the translational operator d/dx which breaks rotational invariance. We suggest that is already the root of free particle quantum mechanics, although one must ultimately create a probability function.

Fermat's Least Time Principle

If one considers that momentum parallel to a target does not change (no impulse), then one has conservation of momentum. This idea may be applied to two dimensional refraction for which the n_1 - n_2 index of refraction surface may be taken as lying along the x axis. Then, one has:

$$P_1 x/\sqrt{xx+AA} = p d/dx \text{ partial} (\sqrt{xx+AA}) = p_2 (x-L)/\sqrt{(x-L)(x-L)+AA} = p_2 d/dx \text{ partial} \sqrt{(x-L)(x-L)+AA} \quad ((2))$$

In other words, one has an equation with two terms adding to 0 with each term containing a d/dx partial. This is the exact form of a maximization problem in x and it may be seen that this is equivalent to maximizing time for a starting point $(0,0)$ moving to $(x,-A)$ in n_1 and then to $((L-x), -2A)$ in n_2 . In other words, one has Fermat's Least Time Principle, but we argue that one is really dealing with the breaking of rotational symmetry in order to find momentum components which either undergo an impulse hit or are conserved.

Momentum Eigenfunction

We argue that mathematically, one may construct a momentum eigenfunction for the operator $-id/dx$ introduced above, namely $\exp(ipx)$. $-id/dx$ is self-adjoint so $\exp(ipx)$ s are orthogonal. At first, this may only seem to be a mathematical formalism to obtain the x -component of p , but the orthogonality feature, together with multiplying $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$ like an AND probability scenario and then multiplying by $\exp(-ip_3x)\exp(-ip_4x)$ leads to automatic conservation of momentum. Thus, we suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ represents a kind of dynamic probability. We have suggested this in previous notes and the argument seems to be strictly classical. In other words, the notion of rotational invariance for p for a free particle and it breaking to account for a p component perpendicular to a target and p components parallel which have momentum conservation leads to the form $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability, or in other words, to free particle quantum mechanics.

Connection With Special Relativity

We note that the Lorentz invariant: $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$, contains $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ which demonstrates rotational invariance. In previous notes, we have also linked free particle quantum mechanics to this invariant because the full free particle probability (wavefunction) is $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$, but here we argue that one may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ simply using the idea of free particle rotational invariance and the breaking of this invariance to account for possible target impulses and momentum conservation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to obtain $\exp(ipx)$ strictly by classical means. We note that a free particle has a momentum magnitude and may move in any direction in space if there are no forces. Thus, there is rotational invariance. This invariance is broken if there is a target which requires an x-y-z co-ordinate axis to describe its position-orientation. In order to describe this quantitatively, one may obtain a particular $p(x)$ component using: $\mathbf{p} \cdot \frac{d}{dx} \text{partial} \sqrt{xx+yy+zz} = p \sin(\theta)$. The translational operator d/dx is linked to the x-component of momentum in a strictly classical manner, as we have described in previous notes. It is possible to find components of p perpendicular to a target so they suffer an impulse, but also parallel, in which case momentum is conserved. The latter, when applied to 2D refraction, leads to Fermat's Least Time Principle, as described above, but is really linked to the breaking of rotational symmetry.

Finally, we note that if one creates an eigenfunction of $-id/dx$ which allows one to obtain the x component of p (which may be useful for an impulse hit or momentum conservation), then because $-id/dx$ is self-adjoint, $\exp(ipx)$ s are orthogonal functions. If one treats $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability, i.e. assigns multiplication for AND situations, and uses $\exp(-i p_{\text{final}} x) \exp(ip_{\text{initial}} x)$, then orthogonality ensures conservation of momentum. Thus, free particle quantum mechanics arises out of free particle rotational invariance and its breaking by d/dx , we argue.